

Funnel-like Expansion of Coverings: Reals defined with Convergence Determine Methods

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Abstract

[한국어] 실수체의 모든 수는 임의의 급수에 대해 수렴된 값일 수 있다. 따라서 실수체의 모든 수는 임의의 급수의 수렴 판별 조건에 대해 참인 속성을 지닌다. 이를 확장 전개하여 실수체에서 정의될 수 있는 모든 덮개를 수렴 판별 조건으로 정의할 수 있다. 이에 따라 실수체 또는 실수체를 기반으로한 모든 체에 대하여 정의된 덮개는 집합의 원소에 대하여 깔때기와 유사한 속성을 지니게 된다.

[English] All the numbers in real field can be converged number from any arbitrary sequence. Therefore, all the numbers in reals have true property against convergence determine methods. Expanding this concept, all the coverings can be defined with convergence determine methods. In conclusion, coverings defined on all the numbers in real field or field based on reals have funnel-like property to target element of set.

1 Introduction

Note that all the notations and definitions follow the case of the referred citation[[김성기\(2011\)](#)]. All the numbers in real field can be converged number from any arbitrary sequence. Therefore, all the numbers in reals have true property against convergence determining methods. There are four kinds of well-known convergence determine methods.

- Alternating series test
- Comparison test
- Root test
- Ratio test

For definition of field, three conditions are needed:

1. Addition, Multiplication Operations
2. Identity, Inverse Elements
3. Associativity, Distributivity

2 Property of Convergence Determine Tests

It is assumed that all the tests are given with condition in axiom of order.

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2.1 Alternating Series Test

With real number sequence $\langle x_n \rangle$:

$$x_1 \geq \cdots \geq x_n \geq x_{n+1} \geq \cdots \geq 0, \lim_n x_n = 0 \implies \sum_n (-1)^{n-1} x_n \text{ converges.}$$

From the alternating series test, a few useful properties can be extracted:

1. Any real number can be a sum of alternating series between negative and positive sign.
2. Any real number can be a sum of sequence which is monotonically decreasing in absolute value.

2.2 Comparison Test

With real number sequence $\langle a_n \rangle, \langle b_n \rangle$:

$$0 \leq a_n \leq b_n, \sum_n b_n \text{ converges} \implies \sum_n a_n \text{ converges.}$$

From the comparison test, a few useful properties can be extracted:

1. Any real number always has equal or larger value in sum of sequence.
2. Any real number always has another sequence converged in equal or larger value.

2.3 Root Test

With real number sequence $\langle a_n \rangle$:

$$\alpha = \limsup_n |a_n|^{1/n}, \alpha < 1 \implies \sum_n a_n \text{ converges.}$$

From the root test, a few useful properties can be extracted:

1. Any real number smaller than one being upper bound of sequence can lead to convergence in sum of sequence.
2. Any converging sequence of real numbers has an upper bound that is defined with infinite multiplication of another convergence less than one.

2.4 Ratio Test

With real number sequence $\langle a_n \rangle$:

$$\alpha_n = \left| \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} \right|, \limsup_n \alpha_n < 1 \implies \sum_n a_n \text{ converges.}$$

From the ratio test, a few useful properties can be extracted:

1. Any ratio sequence in order of real which is consist of between 0 and 1 always derives arbitrary converging sequence.
2. Any real number in sum can have arbitrary converging sequence that is 0 and 1 in ratio between order.

3 Coverings Defined with Convergence Determine Test

It is notable that all the properties extracted in upper occasions can be applied in defining coverings. With changing 'real' into 'covering':

1. Coverings defined with alternation
 - (a) Any covering is a sum of alternating coverings between negative and positive sign.
 - (b) Any covering is a sum in length of coverings which are monotonically decreasing in absolute value.

2. Coverings defined with comparison

- (a) Any covering always has equal or larger value in sum of covering.
- (b) Any covering always has another covering converged in equal or larger interval.

3. Coverings defined with root

- (a) Any covering length smaller than 1 and being upper bound of covering can lead to convergence in sum of covering.
- (b) Any converging sequence of coverings has an upper bound that is defined with infinite multiplication of another covering length less than 1.

4. Coverings defined with ratio

- (a) Any ratio of coverings in order which is consist of length between 0 and 1 always derives arbitrary converging length of coverings.
- (b) Any length of coverings in sum can have arbitrary converging length of coverings that is 0 and 1 in ratio between order.

Any covering given can be defined with upper properties.

4 Funnel-like Expansion of Coverings

Then assuming upper occasions, defining coverings from another coverings that are not equivalent must lead to funnel-like structure. If covering to cover another coverings then at least no equivalence must be assumed. This creates a difference in size of possible number in coverings.

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Assuming that } n(\text{coverings } \forall U) = \aleph_0 \quad (\because \text{countable coverings}) \\ &\implies \text{with family of sets } \{U'_i : i \in I\}, \bigcup_{i \in I} U'_i \supseteq \forall U, \Rightarrow n(\forall U') = \aleph_1 \end{aligned}$$

References

[김성기(2011)] 계승혁 김성기, 김도한. 해석개론(개정판 2판). September 2011.